

Introduction and reception of Agon, a software for more universal access to information society, with an example code of Zoological Vulnerability Guesser

Bishnu Goswami¹

¹Department of Zoology, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan – 713 104, West Bengal,
India.

Author email: bishnu.cert@gmail.com

ORCID of corresponding author: 0000-0002-9473-3947

Abstract

Purpose

The information society of today requires universal access for its benefits to percolate to all human societies. Here we introduce Agon, a software which can be used to write programs in four working languages, including Hindi, Bengali and English, aimed at narrowing the information technology gap among Indian users. Highlights include instant translation between the languages, inclusion of an add-on for a free source code editor, a simple GUI with bold coloring and distinct buttons for more universal access and easy coding for multimedia and internet elements which are often attractive to common users.

Methods

Agon, along with some example codes such as 'Zoological Vulnerability Guesser', was tested for its reception using a survey among secondary and higher secondary students from the town of Burdwan, West Bengal, India. Online mode was chosen, and example videos, code files and the software itself were provided.

Results

Using the USE questionnaire, the results obtained from the survey were overwhelmingly positive. However, the score on "have learned to use it quickly" was on the lower side compared to other items on the questionnaire.

Conclusions

Software like Agon seems to hold ample promise for more universal access to the information society. In the future, a larger project with specific use cases holds promise for successful outcomes in the noble quest.

Keywords: universal access, programming, hindi, education, bengali, zoology

1 Introduction

The use of computer and related information technology (IT) tools have skyrocketed in the recent decades, and with the rise in the availability of information, we have a very sizable 'information society' in our midst. With the rise of smartphones and access to computers, the former becoming more and more universal, the time has never been riper to research about universal access in the information society.

In the newly industrialized country of India[1], the use of computers and information technology has shown a remarkable growth in recent years, some of it being attributed to the Covid-19 pandemic and the associated lockdown[2]. The perception of students towards e-learning that was put into practice during the pandemic, for example, was also studied by researchers[3]. Webinars have been suggested as a future educational tool[4] and for computer education, virtual computer education has been analyzed for its challenges and opportunities[5]. Internet of Things has been pushed forward as a low-cost and effective learning mechanism for STEM education[6] and very recently AI has been used as a potential way for transforming the educational system of India[7].

In the realm of universal access to computing and information society, active research is being conducted throughout the globe for people with disabilities [8][9], however, research is still in its nascent stage in India in that specific context. India, even though newly industrialized, is still lacking access to services in many areas, such as for basic needs[10] or an inclusive education through online mode [11] and therefore access to universal access to the information society seems like a distant dream. Still, previous work for deaf students[12] in India, for visually impaired persons[13] or those with learning disabilities[14], shows promise for a better future for research and development in the area.

In this paper, we introduce a new software Agon, for more universal access to information society among Indian users. This software is aimed to ease the learning curve to simple computer operations, with the demonstration starting from something more complex than clicking links but below what is considered a programming endeavor. Therefore, it can be used by young learners with access to a computer (such as in a public library or home) but without substantial training by teachers or other sources which in practice can often be hard to come by. Agon can be used for

more complex programming and learning tasks too, although examples of such are in active development and not elucidated in this paper. The design of Agon is proactive for universal access, and UI elements are made with distinctness and certain commands are made very simple (such as those for opening websites) so that people with disabilities can leverage their common use cases (browsing through websites of their specific choice easily) by using/writing a simple code. The GUI is also suited for kiosk mode usage, such as in public places like science museums which in India usually have very low entry fees.

The reception of the software was tested on a small cohort in this study for introductory purposes, which included students from secondary and high schools who have at least some basic knowledge about programming.

2 Agon Implementation

Agon (derived from the word 'fire', and applied with the motto of 'igniter of talent and perseverance') is created as a software application to enable its users to make other mini-applications, with its commands in any of the languages among Hindi, Bengali, English, and Simplified English. One of the central paradigms of Agon is these four 'working languages', with two of the languages being very dominant in India (except in the southern states) and having a considerable global diaspora. The English language used here stresses on simple but clear commands, ideal for non-native and younger users. The fourth addition, Simplified English, is aimed to showcase how a program can be coded in very few key presses, making it more palatable to those who feel daunted by technology or feel the learning curve of programming can be very steep, even in the beginner levels. The Bengali module of Agon shares its roots with Bongojontro, a previously developed software[15]. The whole package of Agon comes in at below three megabytes in size, making it suited to be used on older or second-hand, cheaper machines.

Agon is aimed at universal access, especially targeting those users who have or can have very little formal training. The commands used are aimed to support a standard US keyboard, which is the cheapest and most abundantly available, and therefore the commands are typed using the English alphabet keys. The limitations of the phonetics in the standard US keyboard also help the user to avoid ambiguity during coding as many words have multiple spellings in the Bengali or Hindi alphabet. Agon supports a very simple GUI for testing out simple commands, and for more complex and permanent programs, it comes with a separate workflow.

In the workflow for more complex and permanent programs, Agon includes a provision for User Defined Language (UDL) in the free code editing software Notepad ++ (Pronounced Notepad Plus Plus)[16]. The UDL supplied with Agon is called Mahakash (which means the universe, both in Hindi and Bengali). The program coded in Notepad++ can then be copied and run inside the Agon application. With some modifications, the code of the program can be set to run automatically when Agon is run.

2.1 Specifics of the GUI and programming environment

The primary interface of the application is set to be very simple and free of clutter. There are a couple of reasons behind this. Firstly, it is expected to help the user, who is likely to be less experienced, focus on the written code more instead of distractions. Secondly, for universal access, the interface is kept barebones so that if modules for, say, visually challenged or hearing-challenged users are required, they can be incorporated easily. The primary interface is also aimed at supporting kiosk mode operations, in the sense that it can be used in museums, libraries or other public places where economic and other conditions do not allow each user to have their own computer. Apart from the GUI being liberal with partitioning its elements, all buttons and text are of large sizes to accommodate kiosk mode usage.

At the top of the main screen, there are four large-sized buttons that can be clicked, and alternatively, their functions can be executed by keyboard shortcuts listed later. These buttons allow the user to change the working language to one among the four.

FIGURE 1 THE INTERFACE OF AGON, FOUR BIG BUTTONS ON TOP, SIX AT THE BOTTOM.

At the center of the main screen, the commands can be typed in. Agon responds in a very direct manner, and letters start to appear on the screen as they are typed without any initialization procedure. A space after a lower limit of pixels will initiate a newline. As stated earlier, the

interface is intended for very simple commands and is mostly for simple demonstration/teaching purposes. Any program with more than a couple of lines is best done on an external editor, with Notepad++ being recommended, along with the Mahakash UDL.

FIGURE 2 THE LIST OF COMMANDS IN THE FOUR "WORKING LANGUAGES" AS SEEN IN NOTEPAD ++'S UDL SETTINGS

At the bottom of the main screen, there are seven buttons. Five smaller ones have the following functionalities; showing code translated to the current working language, saving the current code on screen, opening the help, restarting the application and quitting the application. The first of the larger button on the lower left is to run the code that is currently displayed on the screen, and it adjusts automatically according to the present working language. The second of the larger buttons executes the code that is copied from a text editor, which should be the path if any program longer than a few lines is to be run.

The interface of Agon is fully operational by the keyboard. Some of these operational highlights in the current version of Agon at the time of writing include:

- Keyboard button F1: Displays help. This specific key is common in many applications for quick help with using the program.
- Keyboard button F2: Save the current typed-in commands to a text file.
- Keyboard button F4: Restarts the application, resetting the choices unless explicitly set by other initialization parameters.
- Keyboard button F5: Sets the working language to Hindi. Also changes the background color to saffron for clarity among users.

- Keyboard button F6: Sets the working language to Bengali. Also changes the background color to violet for clarity among users.
- Keyboard button F7: Sets the working language to Shortened English. Also changes the background color to dark grey for clarity among users.
- Keyboard button F8: Sets the working language to English. Also changes the background color to olive for clarity among users.
- Keyboard button F10: Shows code translated to the current working language. It translates copied code in other working languages to the current one used in the interface.
- Keyboard button F12: Runs code that is copied into memory from an external text editor. It is to be used in the workflow for more complex programs, where the already written code is copied from Notepad ++.

The following figure shows how a code in Hindi is typed in the interface before it is executed in the application. The code outputs a random natural number below 11 for demonstration of simple programming principles. Anything more complex should be used with the workflow for more complex programs, which supports an enhanced text editing experience.

Agon software with Mahakash UDL and a few of its training videos can be downloaded from <https://bishnu.itch.io/agon>. Please note this version is a research version of the software and it should not be used for any sensitive or important work.

FIGURE 3 WRITING A SIMPLE PROGRAM IN HINDI "WORKING LANGUAGE. MORE COMPLEX PROGRAMS SHOULD BE WRITTEN IN NOTEPAD++

2.2 Common Programming Operators and Operations

Irrespective of the current working language, Agon observes some rules about operators. Most of these are common across many of the popular programming languages like Java and JavaScript. These include:

TABLE 1 THE COMMON PROGRAMMING OPERATORS

`	To be placed before writing a command.
;	A statement can be terminated by using a semicolon.
<i>spacebar</i>	After a set span of pixels, adding a space

	will initiate a newline (Only for the inbuilt GUI).
()	Brackets can be used to specify the order of operations
+, -, *, /	Addition, subtraction, multiplication, division.
=	Assignment operator.
==	Compares two variables, returns true if a variable is equal to the other variable.
!=	Compares two variables, returns true if a variable is NOT equal to the other variable.
>	Compares two variables, returns true if the value on the left is greater than the value on the right.
<	Compares two variables, returns true if the value on the left is smaller than the value on the right.
&&	Boolean AND
	Boolean OR
"	Quote for (eg:message) strings.

2.3 Programming commands

Agon supports commands in three working languages; Bengali, Hindi, and English. It has support for another working language, a shorter version for English, bringing the total number of working languages to four. In the below table the equivalent commands for each of the working languages are listed. Please note that all of these commands must be preceded by a "`" symbol (without quotes) to be identified as a command.:

TABLE 2 LIST OF 76 COMMANDS IN THE THEN CURRENT VERSION OF AGON

HINDI	BENGALI	ENGLISH	SIMPLIFIED ENGLISH
<i>sandesh</i>	<i>barta</i>	<i>message</i>	<i>msg</i>

<i>paath_le</i>	<i>nau_lekha</i>	<i>take_text</i>	<i>get</i>
<i>fir_se_suru</i>	<i>abarsuru</i>	<i>start_again</i>	<i>res</i>
<i>agar</i>	<i>jodi</i>	<i>if</i>	<i>if</i>
<i>jabki</i>	<i>cholak</i>	<i>while</i>	<i>whl</i>
<i>anyatha</i>	<i>notuba</i>	<i>else</i>	<i>els</i>
<i>aur_agar</i>	<i>njdi</i>	<i>else_if</i>	<i>eli</i>
<i>text_banau</i>	<i>lekha</i>	<i>to_text</i>	<i>txt</i>
<i>number_banau</i>	<i>sonkha</i>	<i>to_number</i>	<i>num</i>
<i>chitr</i>	<i>chitro</i>	<i>open_photo</i>	<i>pht</i>
<i>chalachitr</i>	<i>jal</i>	<i>open_video</i>	<i>vid</i>
<i>jaal</i>	<i>chalochitro</i>	<i>net</i>	<i>net</i>
<i>patra</i>	<i>nothi</i>	<i>open_document</i>	<i>doc</i>
<i>nirgam</i>	<i>samapti</i>	<i>end_program</i>	<i>kll</i>
<i>ghat</i>	<i>ghat</i>	<i>to_the_power</i>	<i>ttp</i>
<i>tod</i>	<i>vango</i>	<i>break</i>	<i>brk</i>
<i>aniyamit</i>	<i>elomelo</i>	<i>randomize</i>	<i>ran</i>
<i>manzil</i>	<i>mejhe</i>	<i>num_floor</i>	<i>flr</i>
<i>chhat</i>	<i>chad</i>	<i>num_ceil</i>	<i>cei</i>

2.4 Description of the programming commands

The functions of some of the programming commands are tabulated below:

TABLE 3 A SIMPLIFIED TABLE WITH THE DESCRIPTION OF THE PROGRAMMING COMMANDS

Commands	in	Usage
<i>sandesh</i>		Displays a message.
<i>paath_le</i>		Takes a text input from the user for further processing.
<i>fir_se_suru</i>		Restarts the GUI, and also clears the screen.
<i>agar</i>		Implies a condition for a succeeding code block to be executed.
<i>jabki</i>		Starts a loop with a set condition which must be fulfilled in each step.
<i>anyatha</i>		Stands for 'otherwise'. Must be preceded by an if statement and required code blocks.
<i>aur_agar</i>		Stands for 'otherwise' with a second condition.
<i>text_banau</i>		Converts a number to text. useful, for example, when displaying a number as a message.
<i>number_banau</i>		Converts a numeric text to a number. Useful for mathematical operations on the said numeric text.
<i>chitr</i>		Opens a photo file and displays it on the screen.
<i>chalachitr</i>		Opens a video file and plays it automatically.
<i>jaal</i>		Opens a webpage.
<i>patra</i>		Opens a document.
<i>nirgam</i>		Exits the application.

<i>ghat</i>	Raises a number to a power, less than one can be used to extract mathematical roots.
<i>tod</i>	Breaks a loop, used with commands such as "while".
<i>aniyamit</i>	Returns a random number.
<i>manzil</i>	The function takes as input a real number n, and gives as output the greatest integer less than or equal to n.
<i>chhat</i>	The function takes as input a real number n, and gives as output the least integer less than or equal to n.

Users of different working languages can consult the previous table to understand the usage of commands in their own language. Separate tables are omitted here to reduce redundancy, although those tables were used in the succeeding survey work.

2.4 The Mahakash UDL

The UDL is named Mahakash (the universe) to inspire younger users that the sky isn't the limit and with the help of technology one can reach outside the Earth too, such as in the literal usage of information technology to communicate with artificial satellites in the Martian atmosphere. The UDL allows for command syntax highlighting as well as highlighting of the current working language in the Notepad ++ software. Although mixing of working languages is strongly discouraged, it is shown in the figure to show how the syntax of the four working languages looks while used on the editor application.


```
1
2  b=1;
3  `jodi (b<3)
4  {
5
6  b=b+1;
7  `barta ("Hello this is a loop ");
8  `barta ("Nomoskar. Agon ekhon apnader majhe");
9
10
11
12  `barta ("Hello this is a command coded in Bengali")
13  `sandesh ("Hello this is a command coded in Hindi");
14  `message ("Hello this is a command coded in English");
15  `msg ("Hi Hello this is a command coded in Simplified English");
16
17
18
19
20  `jal ("www.openstreetmap.org",o)
21  }
22
```

FIGURE 4 A SAMPLE PROGRAM FOR AGON USING THE MAHAKASH UDL IN NOTEPAD ++

2.5 The "working language translation" feature

Agon is to be used in various settings of universal access, which will include cases where there will be a paucity of teachers and technical support. A core feature of Agon is therefore automatic translation of copied code blocks to the current working language. This will enable commands or full programs written in one working language of Agon to be translated by just a keypress and hopefully will facilitate easier understanding by native language users. All of the four windows in the attached figure show the translated code block from one single code-block with mixed languages. In practice, mixed languages will seldom be encountered and a single language is expected to be used, but the feature is there to format all working languages to any one of the working languages as required by the user. It is worth noting that the translation feature works without additional user input, as in all four cases the F10 button was pressed after changing the working language to one among the four using the keys F5,F6,F7 and F8. This makes Agon suited to be set up in a way to be easily accessible to users with some other handicaps by making some modifications in the software, although those modifications are left out of the scope of this paper.

FIGURE 5 A COLLAGE OF FOUR SCREENSHOTS SHOWING THE "WORKING LANGUAGE TRANSLATION" FEATURE

2.6 Highlighting usability with a basic example program

Agon's usability as a tool for beginner programmers and young learners is put to some initial tests by incorporating some programs along with the software during the survey phase. Some of the programs are very simple, and illustrate the use of a single command, such as the program below in Hindi working language to illustrate the use of if-else commands, text display commands and text entry commands:

```

1
2  ----
3  yedin= `paath_le`("Chutti ke din ","Din likhiye ","gurubar");
4
5  `agar` (yedin=="sombar"||yedin=="mangalbar"
6  ||yedin=="budbar"||yedin=="gurubar"
7  ||yedin=="shukrbar")
8  {
9    `sandesh`("Kam ka hain ye din.");
10 }
11 `aur_agar` (yedin=="shanibar")
12 {
13   `sandesh`("Half day chutti hain");
14 }
15 `anyatha`
16 {
17   `sandesh`("Chutti ka din aj");
18 }
19  ----
20
21

```

FIGURE 6 A SIMPLE PROGRAM IN HINDI "WORKING LANGUAGE" TO ILLUSTRATE IF, ELSE-IF AND ELSE STATEMENTS

In the figure, the automatic highlighting of text is notable. The authors of this paper are also researching the use of Agon for teaching science to students, that work is ongoing.

2.7 Highlighting usability with the educational game "Zoological Vulnerability Guesser"

Zoological Vulnerability Guesser (ZVG) is a game coded using Agon which is educational and fun in nature and is aimed at making the experience of programming attractive for the users while also imparting parallel knowledge about the importance of biodiversity conservation in their regions.

ZVG shows the user one of four animals among tigers, lions, elephants and leopards, all of which are being threatened and at the risk of extinction (exact categories of vulnerability are different for each species). Next, the user has to input their state among a few select choices (to make the program length short and understandable for demonstration purposes). Finally, the users will be asked to input the number of individuals that exists in their own state as per their guess. Finally, the real number of those animals is shown. From reputable sources, the approximate number of tigers[17], lions[18], elephants[19] and leopards[20] were obtained to be coded into ZVG.

ZVG is purposefully made very simple to make it easier to understand by novices. For those more interested, some modifications such as comparing the guessed score to the real score, with a 20% buffer, were described, which added a few more lines.

ZVG in Hindi has the following code (Figure 7). The picture files must reside in the same folder as the Agon app. In the ZVG.zip file in the link given above, the files are in the correct location. ZVG in Bengali and English was also provided to the survey participants.


```
1  `sandesh (" Welcome to Zoological Vulnerability Guesser. Guess the number of shown animals in West Bengal");
2  `sandesh ("Aap ko guess karna hain yeh janawar kitne hain West Bengal main");
3  kaunsi= `chhat ( `aniyamid (4));
4  `agar (kaunsi==1)
5  `chitr ( "tiger.jpg", o);
6  `aur_agar (kaunsi==2)
7  `chitr ( "lion.jpg", o);
8  `aur_agar (kaunsi==3)
9  `chitr ( "elephant.jpg", o);
10 `anyatha
11 `chitr ( "leopard.jpg", o);
12
13 guess= `paath_le ("Jitni tumhara guess","Sankhya likhiye","io");
14 `sandesh ("Aap ne likha:"+ guess+ " Asal main hain: Kebal 96 tigers, 0 lions, 194 elephants aur 83 leopards");
```

FIGURE 7 THE CODE OF THE HINDI VERSION OF ZVG

3 Survey Methodology

3.1 Design

Agon was tested for its likability, usefulness and sustainability as an active part of the secondary and higher educational system in this work. Additionally, verbal dialog was undertaken between the author of this paper and the curators of a few local museums, where Agon is planned to be tested as a programming learning tool in kiosk mode. The participants in the next sections were from schools in and around the town of Burdwan, West Bengal.

The survey aimed to find out how Agon is being received by school students who at least have an introductory background in programming and has access to a personal computer. Demonstration in three languages, i.e. English, Hindi and Bengali was given through video in Google Meet. To encourage users to use the working language they feel comfortable working in, it was made clear that no other working language is better to use than others, and they were asked to try out all three as long as they want to allot for one working language. In the set of example codes provided, the messages inside the code (such as the one which states if an inputted day of the week is a working day or a holiday) were transliterated versions of the English code. The time of use among students who have Hindi, Bengali and English as their first/native language was also measured using a timer inside the application which counts milliseconds past starting the app and changing the working language.

The quantitative part of the surveys was conducted based on the USE questionnaire [21] to get a preliminary picture of the reception of Agon. This questionnaire was chosen as it measures the subjective usability of a product and it is non-proprietary and technology-agnostic. Being a new software product with a fresh paradigm, objective measures to gauge its usability is somewhat unclear at this point, thus the subjective usability was measured first. Additionally, the USE questionnaire has found face validity with relevant and unambiguous descriptions, and its reliability and validity have been reported by previous research [22] to be very positive.

3.2 Target participants

The survey was conducted among students of several secondary schools under the Purba Bardhaman district (under West Bengal, India), with a mix of students of Hindi medium, Bengali medium and English medium students. The video-conferencing app of Google Meet was used. The participants were told to use the software application for four days, with no minimum time of use specified. After four days, they were asked to submit the details through an online form, which contained the USE questionnaire in its digital form. After three more days, form submissions were discontinued.

3.3 Data collection and analysis method

After the completion of four days, the survey-result form (electronic) was opened up for input. Before the submission of the digital forms, the students were instructed on how to fill-up the form in case someone didn't understand the process. Three languages were utilized in the instructions so as not to give preference to any one of the working languages of this work.

After two more days, the survey result form was closed from further input. A total of 53 completely filled-in responses were obtained.

4 Results

4.1 Quantitative results

Using the USE questionnaire, the quantitative aspects of the study were explored. In the first table, the usefulness of Agon software was elucidated. In the context of general-purpose programming by beginners, the responses are shown. This utilized a 1-7 point Likert Scale, where 7 is strongly agreeing with the statement and 1 is strongly disagreeing with the statement. The mean and standard deviation was calculated using the open-source software Libre Office Calc.

TABLE 4 USEFULNESS OF AGON PUT TO THE TEST IN A SURVEY

Statement	Mean score (Between 1-7)	Standard Deviation(up to 2 decimals)
1. It helps me be more effective	5.66	1.13
2. It helps me be more productive	6.15	1.05
3. It is useful	6.5	1.15
4. It makes the things one would want to accomplish easier to get done	5.33	1.22
5. It saves me time when I use it	5.10	1.04
6. It is easy to use	5.23	1.07
7. It is simple to use	6.66	0.96
8. It is user friendly	6.25	1.11

The next table shows the easiness of the operation of the software, here the stress was put to elaborate on the ZVG code in particular.

TABLE 5 THE RESULTS OF THE SURVEY ON THE EASINESS OF OPERATION OF AGON

Statement	Mean score (Between 1-7)	Standard Deviation(up to 3 decimals)
9. It requires the fewest steps possible to accomplish what I want to do with it	6.15	1.14
10. I learned to use it quickly	5.05	1.10
11. I easily remember how to use it	5.9	1.14
12. It is easy to learn to use it	5.12	1.05
13. I am satisfied with it	6.0	1.04

14. I would recommend it to a friend	5.75	0.79
15. It is fun to use	6.1	1.08

It was found from a timer software application that native speakers of Hindi spent more time on the English modules (the average time between two English working languages) than the native speakers of Bengali. For those who study in an English medium school, where the "first language" is English, time spent on Hindi and Bengali working language modes were significantly less.

4.2 Qualitative results

Qualitative data were also gathered from questions and discussions with the students. To summarize, the following points were noted :

- The paradigm of using one's own language, that the student is most comfortable in, was well received.
- The program of ZVG was also well received. Many of the students vastly overestimated the number of flagship but vulnerable biological species such as tigers in their state (estimates ran from 4000-16000 while the actual number is around only 90), and were shocked at the actual numbers.
- The short length of the programs, even in the "English" working language was well received. Younger students tended to be more comfortable with the "English" working language while some of the older students with some experience found "Simplified English" exciting.
- One of the highly praised features was the ability to view a program in a different, native working language. This allowed the students to understand the demonstrations quite fast, without the need of explaining the later example code blocks(which did not come with three working language versions) over and over again.
- Some of the users wanted to design their own websites, and wanted it more than being able to code simple programs.
- In discussion with museum curators, the necessity of conducting workshops to introduce Agon was put forward to the author. However, workshops were not being conducted for the time being.
- Many of the participants loved the ability to run multimedia, especially custom slideshows with only specific images being displayed as per code. This was illustrated to them by a "guess the word" card computer game coded with Agon in the external editor of Notepad++ using Mahakash UDL.
- A few among the participants wanted Agon to be more friendly towards developing simple computer games. It can perhaps be tried in a later version/fork of Agon.

5 Discussion

This work on developing Agon and carrying out the introductory survey highlighted many opportunities in this area. First, there is still a lot of complexity and learning curve for programming in semi-urban and rural places (many of the school students travel to and from their homes in nearby villages) and that is probably one of the additional reasons for the users to choose a very high mean score of 6.66/7 on "it is simple to use". The high average score of 6.5/7 in "it is useful" shows that students do find newer software approaches to basic programming very useful.

The students who have English as their first language spent less time on the other working languages of Agon. The reasons might be they are more comfortable with other programming interfaces, and/or their level of instruction in schools (which are private and relatively expensive) is better. This possibly shows a problem with universal access, where the access to programming education is lacking for people from lower socioeconomic strata, however, it should be studied with a much larger, possibly nationwide survey.

The ability of Agon to create more complex programs, using commands to display images, videos and websites following the programmer's algorithm merits its use for more elaborate projects. The versatile nature of swapping the working programming language can be put to use in top-down workflows for better efficiencies. For example, a software module to collect epidemiological surveys and be understandable to all the leaders of the cohort can be put through this "swapping working language" paradigm, not necessarily using Agon derivatives but also with other software. It must be understood in this context that there are many regions throughout India and developing countries worldwide where even knowing English is a luxury, let alone English programs with English documentation. Therefore projects like Agon can be useful for universal access to technology. Additionally, with some modifications to Agon, it can also be made more accessible to visually challenged people or people with other disabilities.

In the context of education, Agon can be used as a tool to create interactive educational content which can be used offline and can be used without any cost/subscription. The good scores on the reception of the ZVG code illustrate this point.

6 Conclusion

We created Agon, a software program that is simple to use and supports commands in four different "working languages". These languages include Hindi and Bengali, two very dominant languages in Northern India with a sizable global diaspora and English. In English, two types of languages, one for clarity and the other to reduce command size for faster coding was utilized. The highlights also include the ability to handle multimedia files and webpages in single-line commands, which makes it easy to build simple but rich software and games. The interface and the working languages were proactively built with universal access in mind, where people without the access to months or years of training can code simple programs and create a custom flow of multimedia and webpage access. For more complex programs, an UDL called Mahakash was also built for an external, free source code editor.

In the survey that was conducted to explore the initial reception of the Agon software among school students of secondary and high schools, the response was very positive. Included in the survey was a demonstration of the software in its different working languages and it was a significant factor in its likability. Some simple programs and the ZVG code were demonstrated and were received very positively by the survey participants. To sum up, Agon seemed like a viable candidate and a step forward for universal access in the technological society of today.

7 Limitations of this study and future work

One of the limitations of this study was the limited comparison of usefulness between the English and the Simplified English working languages. Using more complex and longer code, along with more experienced students and perhaps professionals can be a scope for future work, and currently, a work around STEM education is being done with Agon. Secondly, working with younger students who have just started out computing can also be tested and their responses can be used to build better software. Thirdly, more languages can be added, including those languages which are vulnerable to the threat of extinction in the country. In that way, the dying languages can have a new lease of life as technology education and use is growing at an amazing pace. Finally, specific target groups with disabilities can be targeted in future work for more universal access to the information society of the near and far future.

Funding

The author acknowledges the funding of University Grants Commission of India for the UGC-SRF fellowship during carrying out of this work.

Statements and Declarations

Competing interests: The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

REFERENCES

- [1]Paweł Bożyk (2006). "Newly Industrialized Countries". [*Globalization and the Transformation of Foreign Economic Policy*](#). Ashgate Publishing, Ltd. p. 164. [ISBN 0-7546-4638-6](#).
- [2]Kumar, A., & Pathak, P. (2020). The Pros and Cons of Virtual Learning in India: An Insight During'Covid Lockdown'. *Adhyayan: A Journal of Management Sciences*, 10(01), 08-13.
- [3]Punjani, K. K., & Mahadevan, K. (2022). Transitioning to online learning in higher education: Influence of Awareness of COVID-19 and Self-Efficacy on Perceived Net Benefits and Intention. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(1), 291-320.
- [4] Gupta, S. K., & Sengupta, N. (2021). Webinar as the future educational tool in higher education of India: A survey-based study. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 26(4), 1111-1130.
- [5] Bhattacharya, P., Joshi, S., Bandyopadhyay, S., & Mittal, R. Virtual Computer Science Education in India: Challenges and Opportunities.

- [6] Chawla, S. (2021). Design and implementation of IoT based Low cost, effective learning mechanism for empowering STEM education in India. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(13), 125-133.
- [7] Jaiswal, A., & Arun, C. J. (2021). Potential of Artificial Intelligence for Transformation of the Education System in India. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 17(1), 142-158.
- [8] Johansson, S., Gulliksen, J., & Gustavsson, C. (2021). Disability digital divide: the use of the internet, smartphones, computers and tablets among people with disabilities in Sweden. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 20(1), 105-120.
- [9] Ferm, U., Ekström, A., Larsson, E., & Samuelsson, C. (2021). Tablet computer-supported conversation between people with dementia and their carers: technology as interactional focus. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 20(4), 753-765.
- [10] Trindade, T. C., MacLean, H. L., & Posen, I. D. (2021). Slum infrastructure: Quantitative measures and scenarios for universal access to basic services in 2030. *Cities*, 110, 103050.
- [11] Ware, N. D. (2021). Online education in India and the widening digital divide. In *Handbook of Research on Inequities in Online Education During Global Crises* (pp. 494-509). IGI Global.
- [12] Joy, J., Balakrishnan, K., & Madhavankutty, S. (2021). SignText: a web-based tool for providing accessible text book contents for Deaf learners. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 1-7.
- [13] Senjam, S. S., Foster, A., & Bascaran, C. (2021). Barriers to using assistive technology among students with visual disability in schools for the blind in Delhi, India. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, 16(7), 802-806.
- [14] Bansal, G., & Singh, A. P. (2021). Computer-Assisted Cognitive Re-Training as An Intervention for Children with Specific Learning Disability: A Review.
- [15] Goswami, B., & Pal, S. (2022). Introduction of two new programming tools in Bengali and measurement of their reception among high-school students in Purba Bardhaman, India with the prototypic inclusion of a vector-biology module. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(2), 1585-1607.
- [16] <https://github.com/notepad-plus-plus/notepad-plus-plus>
- [17] <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/kolkata/west-bengal-to-release-14-tigers-in-buxa-national-park-minister/articleshow/84825991.cms>
- [18] https://www.wwfindia.org/about_wwf/priority_species/threatened_species/asiatic_lion/
- [19] <http://www.walkthroughindia.com/wildlife/12-states-with-highest-number-of-wild-elephants-in-india/>
- [20] YV Jhala (2020) LEOPARDS - Press Information Bureau
- [21] Lund, A. M. (2001). Measuring usability with the USE questionnaire. *Usability Interface*, 8(2), 3-6.
- [22] Gao, M., Kortum, P., & Oswald, F. (2018). Psychometric Evaluation of the USE (Usefulness, Satisfaction, and Ease of use) Questionnaire for Reliability and Validity. *Proceedings of the Human*

Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting, 62(1), 1414–1418.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1541931218621322>